

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of hetero binuclear Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes

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Abstract : A series of transition metal Schiff base ligand complexes derived from *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) were synthesized. The general composition of the complexes is $M_aL.M_bL'$, where $M_a = Cu$, $M_b = Rb$ or Cs , $L = N,N'$ -1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) (ES) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) (PS), $L' =$ deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline. The complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, infrared spectra and UV-Visible spectra. The metal chelate of Schiff base acts as bidentate ligand and coordinates through phenolic oxygen atoms. The hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC 739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and for antifungal activity against fungus *Candida albicans* MTCC 227.

Keywords : Schiff base complexes, IR spectra, UV-Visible spectra, antimicrobial studies, MIC.

Introduction

Metal complexes of Schiff bases have been extensively studied due to their novel structural features, unusual magnetic properties and relevance to biological systems^{1,2}. Schiff base complexes are important for designing metal complexes related to synthetic and natural oxygen carriers³ and exhibit numerous biological activities such as anticancer, antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal, etc.^{4,5}. Gruber *et al.*^{6,7} have reported the synthesis of oxygen bridged complexes of the type $M_aL_2.M_bL'_2$, where M_a was metal with tetradentate salicylaldimines (L), M_aL_2 is metal salicylaldimines (i.e. CuES or NiES) which acted as a bidentate ligand on complexation with metal halides $M_bL'_2$ (i.e. CuCl₂, NiCl₂ etc.) to which it coordinates through two phenolic oxygen atoms.

In the present paper, we report a series of new hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes of the type $M_aL.M_bL'$, where $M_a = Cu$, $M_b = Rb$ or Cs , $L = N,N'$ -1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine), $L' =$ deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline

Results and discussion

The physical properties of heterobinuclear complexes

of *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldiminato)copper(II) (CuES) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldiminato)-copper(II) (CuPS) metal chelate with rubidium or cesium metal salts of some organic acids are listed in Table 1. The complexes are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, DMF and DMSO but insoluble in water. Molar conductivities of all these complexes were measured in DMSO at 20 (± 0.5) °C and at a concentration of 10^{-3} M. Low value (0.6–6.2 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of molar conductivity of the complexes indicate that they are covalent in nature⁸.

Infrared spectra :

CuES, CuPS and their hetero binuclear rubidium or cesium metal complexes exhibit infrared bands in the region 1527–1598 cm^{-1} (Table 2). These bands arise due to C–O stretching in these compounds⁹. The position of infrared bands near 1530 cm^{-1} arising in various transition metal Schiff base complexes has been assigned to C–O stretching by several authors^{10–13}. The mononuclear metal complex, CuES and CuPS exhibits ν_{C-O} str. (phenolic) at 1546 and 1538 cm^{-1} respectively which shifts toward higher energy side (with few exceptions) on complexation with rubidium or cesium metal salts of organic acids indicating the coordination through the phenolic oxy-

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the hetero binuclear Schiff base complexes

Compd.	Colour	Melt.(m) Dec.(d)/Trans.(t) temp. (°C)	Molar cond. (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	μ^{eff} (B.M.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Cald.)					Yield (%)
					C	H	N	M _a	M _b	
CuES.RbTNP	Yellow	225m	3.3	1.18	39.52 (41.05)	2.50 (2.48)	10.75 (10.88)	9.75 (9.88)	12.85 (13.29)	50.12
CuES.CsTNP	Yellow	215d	2.9	2.15	37.45 (38.23)	2.33 (2.31)	9.75 (10.13)	8.92 (9.20)	18.90 (19.23)	40.24
CuES.CsDNP	Deep yellow	240d	3.1	1.82	38.22 (39.33)	2.48 (2.43)	8.65 (9.13)	7.92 (7.20)	17.20 (17.43)	41.54
CuES.Rb1N2N	Brown	260d	2.7	1.95	52.28 (53.14)	3.42 (3.40)	6.92 (7.15)	10.68 (10.82)	14.45 (14.56)	60.73
CuES.Cs1N2N	Brownish green	260md	2.9	2.25	47.95 (49.17)	3.10 (3.15)	6.50 (6.61)	9.70 (10.01)	20.25 (20.94)	50.42
CuES.Rb8HQ	Green	260d	0.6	Dia.	52.50 (53.66)	3.53 (3.57)	6.98 (7.51)	10.95 (11.36)	14.90 (15.29)	30.08
CuES.Cs8HQ	Pale green	200m	1.2	Dia.	47.90 (49.46)	3.25 (3.29)	6.75 (6.92)	9.58 (10.47)	21.28 (21.91)	40.89
CuPS.RbTNP	Yellow	200m	3.8	1.81	40.95 (42.00)	2.86 (2.73)	10.20 (10.65)	9.48 (9.6)	12.68 (13.01)	60.02
CuPS.CsTNP	Light brown	218m	2.1	2.2	38.78 (39.17)	2.52 (2.55)	9.75 (9.93)	8.75 (9.01)	18.35 (18.86)	68.12
CuPS.RbDNP	Brown	270d	6.2	Dia.	44.32 (45.09)	2.98 (3.10)	8.90 (9.15)	10.05 (10.38)	13.70 (13.96)	50.21
CuPS.Rb1N2N	Brown	210m	3.1	Dia.	52.82 (53.90)	3.62 (3.66)	6.52 (6.98)	10.25 (10.57)	13.94 (13.98)	30.69
CuPS.Cs1N2N	Deep brown	220t	2.8	1.78	48.75 (49.96)	3.35 (3.39)	6.28 (6.47)	9.28 (9.79)	19.80 (20.49)	35.24
CuPS.Cs8HQ	Yellowish green	270d	1.3	1.4	48.75 (50.28)	3.56 (3.54)	6.38 (6.76)	9.95 (10.24)	20.08 (21.42)	36.24
CuPS.Rb8HQ	Yellowish green	260d	0.7	1.79	53.52 (54.44)	3.85 (3.83)	7.08 (7.32)	10.68 (11.08)	13.95 (14.91)	38.20
CuPS.CsONP	Brown	220m	0.8	Dia.	44.50 (44.91)	3.26 (3.25)	6.68 (6.83)	9.98 (10.34)	21.50 (21.63)	50.70
CuPS.RbONP	Light brown	240m	2.2	1.88	48.50 (48.67)	3.50 (3.52)	7.35 (7.04)	10.95 (11.20)	14.86 (15.07)	40.44

where m – sharp melting point, d – decomposition temperature, md – melting with decomposition and t – transition temperature.

gen. The major shift of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ str. (phenolic) by 52 cm^{-1} in the hetero binuclear complexes certainly indicates the presence of phenoxo bridge. The bands in the far infrared region i.e. $430\text{--}499$ and $502\text{--}581 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the hetero binuclear complexes are tentatively assigned to M–N str. and M–O str. modes respectively¹⁴. These bands are not present in the ligand, *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldehyde) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldehyde). In the neutral

transition metal chelate, CuES, the band at 465 and 520 cm^{-1} are assigned to M–N str. and M–O str. respectively while in CuPS, the M–N str. vibration arises at 466 cm^{-1} whereas M–O str. vibration occurs at 505 cm^{-1} .

UV-Visible spectra :

The electronic absorption bands (Table 2) for the chelate neutral complexes of Cu^{II} metal of ligands *N,N'*-1,2-

Table 2. Spectral data of Cu^{II} metal chelate and their hetero binuclear complexes

Compd.	Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)			UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (in nm)
	$\nu(\text{C-O})$ phenolic	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	
CuES	1546	520	465	245, 312, 387, 562
CuES.RbTNP	1546, 1567	536	430	245, 341, 387
CuES.CsTNP	1565	514	432	245, 312, 348, 392
CuES.Rb8HQ	1574	520	435	250, 384
CuES.Cs8HQ	1528, 1575	519	465	236, 312
CuES.Rb1N2N	1533, 1598	570, 502	435	238, 358
CuES.Cs1N2N	1531	571	465, 499	233, 353
CuES.CsDNP	1530	573, 528	466	243, 348, 380, 562
CuPS	1538	505	466	219, 242, 263, 352, 652
CuPS.RbTNP	1552	518	490	250, 344
CuPS.CsTNP	1550	515	480	231, 351
CuPS.RbDNP	1540	528	410	233, 244, 342, 351, 356
CuPS.Rb8HQ	1574	581, 520	406	236, 332, 382
CuPS.Cs8HQ	1574	521	406	246, 363
CuPS.Rb1N2N	1532	531	466	226, 231, 252, 260, 276
CuPS.Cs1N2N	1527	518	455	221, 231, 262, 267, 276
CuPS.RbONP	1542	540	457	236, 341, 380
CuPS.CsONP	1537	545	468	248, 344, 555

ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) and *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) observed between 219–312 nm indicates $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in aromatic ring and C=N chromophore. The bands appearing between 352–652 nm in Cu^{II} complexes (i.e. CuES and CuPS) show charge transfer and *d-d* transition^{13,15}. The spectra of all Cu^{II} bridge complexes in the range 312–562 nm suggest that there is no changes in stereochemistry of complexes after adduct formation. The bands of the hetero binuclear complexes in the range 312–562 nm may be attributed to charge transfer whereas bands in the range 221–276 nm is due to internal ligand transition. The absorption bands of medium intensity in CuES and CuPS at 387 and 352 nm respectively indicates square planar geometry¹⁶ of Cu²⁺ with coordination number 4. Similar type of electronic spectral bands are observed in the hetero binuclear complexes of CuES and CuPS with rubidium or cesium metal salts of organic acids suggesting similar square planar geometry of CuES and CuPS in all its hetero binuclear adducts. As the coordination number of Cu²⁺ in CuES and CuPS remains the same in the hetero binuclear complexes, it indicates that Cu²⁺ doesn't get attached with

rubidium or cesium metal salts of organic acids on complexation. No absorption bands have been found in the region 700–1200 nm in the hetero binuclear complexes which further confirms that the coordination number of Cu²⁺ in the hetero binuclear adducts have not been raised but it remains 4 with square planar geometry. The magnetic moment values of the hetero binuclear adducts of CuES and CuPS lies between 1.78–2.25 B.M. which correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron and the square planar geometry¹⁶ with coordination number 4. In CuES.Rb8HQ, CuES.Cs8HQ, CuPS.RbDNP, CuPS.Rb1N2N and CuPS.CsONP, the spin of the Cu^{II} ions are so strongly coupled that they show diamagnetic behaviour¹².

The bonding between *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldiminato)metal(II) complex (M_aES) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldiminato)metal(II) complex (M_aPS) with the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the IR spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of the adducts. The physico-chemical studies as discussed above suggests

square planar geometry of M_aES and M_aPS (where $M_a = Cu^{II}$) with coordination number 4 in all its alkali metal

Fig. 1. Probable structure for the hetero binuclear Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes having general formula $M_aL.M_bL'$, where $M_a = Cu$, $M_b = Rb$ or Cs .

adducts. The probable structure and bonding of the newly prepared compounds with general formula ($M_aL.M_bL'$) may be shown as in Fig. 1.

Antimicrobial activity :

The *in vitro* antimicrobial screening to the synthesized hetero binuclear complexes were carried out against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC 739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and fungi *Candida albicans* MTCC 227. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values of the investigated complexes are given in Table 3. The antimicrobial activity of the complexes can be considered on the basis of chelation theory. Chelation causes overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with the donor groups. This reduces the polarity of the metal ion considerably and there is increase in the delocalization of π -electrons

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities (MIC values) of some of the investigated hetero binuclear Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
	MTCC 739	MTCC 96	MTCC 227
CuES.RbTNP	200	200	100
CuES.CsDNP	25	100	100
CuES.Rb1N2N	50	50	50
CuPS.RbTNP	50	100	50
CuPS.RbDNP	50	50	100
CuPS.Rb1N2N	25	50	50
Streptomycin	100	25	-
Fluconazole	-	-	100

over the whole chelate ring. Also, there is enhancement in the penetration through the lipid layers of the cell membrane resulting in interference of the normal cell process of the organisms which restricts further growth of the organisms¹⁷

Experimental

A.R. grade reagents have been used for synthesizing all the complexes. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model 8201PC in KBr phase. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UVB VIS spectrophotometer. Melting point of the compounds was determined on electrical tempo T-1150 melting point apparatus. Molar conductivities were measured with the help of Systronic digital direct conductivity meter-306. Magnetic measurements were carried on Faraday Magnetic Susceptibility balance. Cu^{II} ion has been estimated by complexometric EDTA titrations; estimation of Rb and Cs were done by standard methods¹⁸.

Synthetic procedures :

Cu^{II} metal complex of the Schiff base N,N'-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) :

The Schiff base of *N,N'*-1,2-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) was prepared by refluxing the salicylaldehyde and 1,2-ethylenediamine in 2 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol for 10 min. The yellow coloured Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ice cold ethanol and dried. A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring to a hot

solution of the Schiff base (ES, 2.81 g). The mixture was further refluxed with constant stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The solution upon cooling deposited purple coloured copper complex. It was filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Cu^{II} metal complex of the Schiff base N,N'-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) :

The Schiff base of *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldimine) was prepared by refluxing the salicylaldehyde and 1,2-propylenediamine in 2 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol for 10 min. The yellow coloured Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ice cold ethanol and dried. A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring to a hot solution of the Schiff base (PS, 2.82 g). The mixture was further refluxed with constant stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The solution upon cooling deposited purple coloured copper complex. It was filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Hetero binuclear complexes constituting Cu^{II} metal ion and rubidium or cesium metal :

N,N'-1,2-Ethylenebis(salicylaldiminato)copper(II) (CuES) or *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(salicylaldiminato)-copper(II) (CuPS) was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and rubidium or cesium metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or 8-hydroxyquinoline were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with constant stirring for 50 min. The characteristic coloured adducts were precipitated in hot condition which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried in an electric oven at 80 °C.

Antimicrobial activity :

The hetero binuclear complexes have been tested for *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC 739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and fungi *Candida albicans* MTCC 227 by microplate method of Eloff¹⁹, using broth nutrient as the medium. Different dilution of chemical were prepared in

DMSO solvent and added to the well. The microplates were incubated at 37 (±1) °C and examined after 12 h and reabsorbed after 48 h. After 48 h, each was screened and lowest dilution of the chemical without any growth of the organism was recorded as MIC. These test organisms were also checked with some antibiotics like streptomycin and antifungal like fluconazole.

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